

Studies on Potential Pesticides. Part VIII Synthesis of O,O-Dialkyl S-[2-(Phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-Oxadiazol-5-] Dithiophosphate and O,O-Dialkyl O-[2-(Phenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-Oxadiazol-5-Thione-4-Methyl-] Dithiophosphate.

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Twenty three new organophosphorous compounds have been synthesised by the condensation of O,O-dialkyl chlorothio-phosphate with several 2-phenoxy-methyl-5-mercapto 1,3,4-oxadiazole and 2-phenoxy-methyl 4-hydroxymethyl 1,3,4-oxadiazole 5-thione. Nine compounds were tested for their anti-acetyl-cholinesterase activity.

ORGANOPHOSPHATES exhibiting potent anti-acetyl cholinesterase activities^{1,2} have been used extensively as important insecticides^{3,4}. The insecticidal properties of condensation products of chloromethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole and thiadiazoles with potassium dialkyl phosphorothiolothionates were reported⁵. A number of oxadiazole compounds were reported as insecticides, miticides and bactericides^{6,7}. Recently Sengupta *et al.* observed the bactericidal properties of oxadiazole derivatives. Pianka reported the pesticidal properties of organophosphorous compounds containing oxadiazole and thiazoles^{8,9}. With a view to study the acetyl cholinesterase inhibition properties and insecticidal activity, we synthesised several compounds by condensing O, O-dialkyl chlorothio phosphate with several 2-phenoxy methyl-5-mercapto 1,3,4-oxadiazole and 2-phenoxy methyl 4-hydroxymethyl 1,3,4-oxadiazole-5-thione.

In all twenty three compounds have been synthesised by replacing the active hydrogen of I and II by O,O-dialkyl chlorothiophosphate.

The detailed activity of these compounds will be published elsewhere.

Experimental

O,O-dialkyl chlorothiophosphate was prepared according to the method of Fletcher *et al.*¹⁰. Thiophosphorylchloride was prepared after the method of Belar¹¹.

0,0-Dipropyl chlorothiophosphate

Thiophosphorylchloride (20 g) in dry benzene (50 ml) was added under constant stirring to a solution of sodium n-propoxide (from 5.5 g of Na in 75 ml of propanol). The reaction temperature being kept at 5-10°. After complete addition the mixture was filtered and filtrate concentrated in vacuum. The product distilled at 130/3 mm. yield 50%.

2(2,4 Dichloro phenoxy-methyl) 1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-thiones was synthesised following Youngs method¹². A suspension of 0.1 mole of 2,4-Dichloro phenoxyacetic acid hydrazide, 0.1 mole of potassium hydroxide and .11 mole of carbondisulphide was refluxed on steam-bath for twelve hours. The reaction mixture cooled, solvent distilled off and residue dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid; solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol. Other thiones were synthesised by the similar method. The analysis, m.p.s are recorded in Table 1.

4-hydroxymethyl-2-(4-chlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-thione.

To a suspension of 0.1 mole of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy-methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-thione in 100 ml ethanol was added 1.0 g (40%) formaldehyde. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature, separated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. M.P. and analysis of the title compounds are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 1

Compd. no.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.P.°C	Molecular formula	% of N	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	Cl	H	Cl	147	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	10.68	10.11
2.	H	H	Cl	159	C ₉ H ₇ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	12.01	11.57
3.	CH ₃	H	H	121	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	12.26	12.61
4.	H	CH ₃	H	96-7	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	12.84	12.61
5.	H	H	CH ₃	149	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	12.78	12.61

TABLE 2

Compd. No.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	M.P.°C	Molecular formula	% of N	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	Cl	H	Cl	137	C ₁₀ H ₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	9.48	9.12
2.	H	H	Cl	123	C ₁₀ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	10.15	10.29
3.	CH ₃	H	H	100-1	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S	11.42	11.11
4.	H	CH ₃	H	79-81	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	11.24	11.11
5.	H	H	CH ₃	124	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ S	11.34	11.11

0,0-dialkyl S-[2-(*p*-methyl phenoxy)methyl] 1, 3, 4-oxadiazolyl-5-] dithiophosphate

A mixture of corresponding O,O-dialkyl chlorothio-phosphate (1 M) and 5-mercapto 2-(*p*-methyl phenoxy-methyl) 1,3,4-oxadiazole (1 M) was refluxed in dry acetone for twelve hours under stirring in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate. Filtered and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Solid obtained was crystallised from ethyl alcohol M.p.s are recorded in table 3.

0,0-dialkyl O-2(*p*-chloro phenoxy)methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-thione-4-methyl) dithiophosphate.

Mixture of corresponding O,O-dialkyl chlorothio-phosphate (0.01 M) and 4-hydroxymethyl [2-(*p*-chloro phenoxy)methyl]-1,3,4-oxadiazol]-5-thione in dry acetone was refluxed in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate for twelve hours under stirring. Filtered and solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Solid obtained was crystallised from ethyl acetate, M.p.s are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3 (a)

Comp. No.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R	M.P. °C	Molecular formula
1.	Cl	H	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	191-93	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
2.	H	H	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	197-99	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
3.	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	176	C ₁₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
4.	H	H	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	212-14	C ₁₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
5.	Cl	H	Cl	nC ₃ H ₇	189	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
6.	H	H	Cl	nC ₃ H ₇	212	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ClN ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
7.	CH ₃	H	H	nC ₃ H ₇	185-86	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
8.	H	H	CH ₃	nC ₃ H ₇	204	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
9.	Cl	H	Cl	nC ₄ H ₉	184	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
10.	H	H	Cl	nC ₄ H ₉	188-90	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ ClN ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
11.	CH ₃	H	H	nC ₄ H ₉	201-3	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂
12.	H	H	CH ₃	nC ₄ H ₉	222-3	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₄ PS ₂

TABLE 3 (b)

Comp. No.	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R	M.P. °C	Molecular formula
13.	Cl	H	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	189	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
14.	H	H	Cl	C ₂ H ₅	200-2	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ ClN ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
15.	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂ H ₅	178	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
16.	H	H	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	182	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
17.	Cl	H	Cl	nC ₃ H ₇	211	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
18.	H	H	Cl	nC ₃ H ₇	204	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ ClN ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
19.	CH ₃	H	H	nC ₃ H ₇	167	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
20.	H	H	CH ₃	nC ₃ H ₇	188	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
21.	Cl	H	Cl	nC ₄ H ₉	182	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
22.	H	H	Cl	nC ₄ H ₉	179	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ ClN ₂ O ₅ PS ₂
23.	H	H	CH ₃	nC ₄ H ₉	199	C ₁₈ H ₂₉ N ₂ O ₅ PS ₂

- All the m.p.s were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected, elemental analysis of the compounds were found satisfactory.
- Yield of the compounds ranges between 50 to 80%.

Determination of acetylcholinesterase activity.

The method of Hestrin¹³ as described by Colwick and Kaplan¹⁴ was used to determine anti-AchE activity. Compounds were dissolved in water and used at a conc. of $3 \times 10^{-4} M$. A control containing equal volume of water was also run in parallel. Compound No. 3,4,6, 8,10,11,17&18 were tested but only three compounds (3,4 and 10) showed marginal inhibition.

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References

1. R. D. O. BRIEN, *Metabolic inhibitors*, Vol. II. Edited by R. M. HOCHSTER and J. H. QUASTEB, Academic Press Inc., New York, 205, 1963.

2. B. HOLMOTED, *Pharmacol. Rev.*, 1959, 11, 567.
 3. J. E. CASIDA, *J. Agr. Food. Chem.*, 1956, 4, 1772.
 4. T. R. FACUTO, *Advan. Pest Control. Res.*, 1957, 1, 147.
 5. J. R. GIEGY, A., G.B.P. 978, 854/1964.
 6. Jap. P. 70 17. 189 (1970), *C.A.*, 1970, 73, 77252Y.
 7. Jap. P. 70 24. 982 (1970), *C.A.*, 1970, 73, 98953 t.
 8. M. J. PIANKA, *Sci. Fd. Agric.*, 1968, 19, 403.
 9. M. J. PIANKA, *Sci. Fd. Agric.*, 1967, 18, 63.
 10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3943.
 11. "Inorganic Synthesis" Vol. N. p. 71.
 12. R. W. YOUNG and K. H. WOOD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 400.
 13. S. HESTRIN, The reaction of acetylcholine and other carboxylic acid derivatives with hydroxylamine and its analytical application.
 14. S. P. COLOWICK and N. O. KAPLAN, "Methods in enzymology, Academic Press", New York.